

Project BioCombs4Nanofibers

D2.3 Report on lab-scale fiber production

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1. Goals and Detailed Description

D2.3 is a public report about the lab-scale fiber production methods used in the project by partners **RWTH**, **ELMARCO**, and **JKU**. It will be published on the **BioCombs4Nanofibers** website as well as on the Zenodo open data depository. According the deliverable D5.2 Data Management Plan (DMP) - interim, it contains, among others, the spinning material systems (including recipes), spinning parameters (e.g., pressures, flow rates and fiber collection rates), and SEM micrographs of natural and microfluidic-spun fibers from partner **RWTH** and electrospinning conditions, SEM micrographs, and fiber diameter measurements from partner **ELMARCO**.

Out of the six partners in the **BioCombs4Nanofibers** consortium, three work on the production of nano- and microfibers. **ELMARCO** produces equipment for industrial- and lab-scale electrospinning of nanofibers. The structured foils prepared in WP3 (compare deliverables D3.1, D3.2, D3.3) will be integrated into these devices to facilitate handling the produced nanofibers. Therefore, samples are produced and sent to **JKU** and **RWTH** to test the antiadhesive properties of the structured substrates.

With **ELMARCO**'s professional advice, **JKU** has established a setup for lab-scale production of nanofibers via needle-less electrospinning. This setup operates with small polymer solution volumes (20 - 50 ml) and the collecting plate is easily accessible for quick sample changes, thus allowing performing preliminary tests of the developed structured materials at **JKU** before sending the materials to **ELMARCO** for thorough evaluation.

RWTH is establishing microfluidic fiber spinning as an alternative to electrospinning for the production of nano- and microfibers. While microfluidic fiber spinning allows a wider range of polymerization mechanisms and larger diameters, the technology is at a lower technological readiness level compared to electrospinning.

JKU's lab-scale electrospinning setup is shown in **Image 1**. A silver wire (diameter 0.4 mm) is spun over a rotating Teflon cylinder (diameter ~ 45 mm) thus creating effectively four wire electrodes (each 30 mm long). As the drum is rotated, the wires are immersed into the polymer solution one after the other. Subsequently, each wire coated in polymer solution is then brought

into the electric field where electrospinning occurs. The electrospun fiber mats are deposited onto a stationary metal plate (approx. 12 cm²) that can house substrates of interest (i.e., structured foils) given that the substrate is smaller than the metal plate. The receiving plate can be adjusted to vary the distance between the spinning electrodes to achieve the desired electric field strength.

Image 1: Overview of the nozzle-less electrospinning setup at JKU. A) Fully assembled setup: 1 – rotating cylinder with four wire electrodes, 2 – container for the polymer solution, 3 – receiving electrode magnetically fixed onto an adjustable plate, 4 – high voltage connection, 5 – motor for the cylinder rotation. B) A close-up of the rotating cylinder with wire electrodes.

The entire setup is enclosed in a plastic container that has a custom-made ventilation/dehumidification unit attached to it. Although the dehumidifier is not powerful enough to decrease relative humidity below 40 %, it allows maintaining conditions inside of the electrospinning chamber below 55 % relative humidity (usually 45 - 50 % RH). In absence of the ventilation/dehumidifier unit, humidity can rapidly reach 80 % which renders the electrospinning process impossible. Samples are prepared by spinning the polymer solution until the fiber mat is visibly white but slightly translucent (usually approximately 1 – 2 min of electrospinning).

Polyamide 6 (PA6) was selected as a polymer of choice for electrospinning experiments at JKU. Fiber mats of Polyamide 6 are spun from acetic/formic acids medium according to a recipe provided by **ELMARCO** (12 wt% solution of PA6 in acetic and formic acids).

Fiber mats with fiber diameters of 150 - 250 nm were electrospun onto a selection of substrates to assess the fiber mat's peeling ability from various materials as well as from structured and unstructured surfaces. The peeling ability was assessed non-quantitatively by removing the fiber mat with tweezers at an obtuse angle, and the peeled-off area was inspected under the scanning electron microscope (Phillips 525 SEM, Phillips, Germany) after sputter-coating with 10 - 20 nm of gold (Bal-Tec SCD 005 Sputter Coater, BAL-TEC GmbH, Germany). **Image 2** shows a SEM micrograph of polyamide-6 electrospun fibers on surfaces with nano- and microripples. Detailed results of the assessment of the fibers' peeling ability from various structured and unstructured materials can be found in deliverable D2.4 Adhesion measurement of natural and artificial fibers.

Image 2: Examples of SEM micrographs of polyamide-6 electrospun fiber mats onto surfaces with nanoripples (A, B) and microripples (C, D). A. Laser-processed PET foil with nanoripples covered with PA6 electrospun fiber mat; substantial amount of fibers present in the peeled-off region (right of the tear line). B. Close-up of A; nanoripples can be recognized under the fibers. C. Silicone imprint of a 1- μm diffraction foil with all fibers cleanly peeled off. D. Several PA6 electrospun fibers on the silicone imprint of the 1- μm diffraction foil; it is noticeable that fibers rest on the topmost features of the substrate.

First samples were produced at **ELMARCO** and sent to **JKU** and **RWTH** to test the antiadhesive properties of the structured substrate. **ELMARCO**'s commercially available electrospinning device NS1S500U (needle-free) was used to prepare fiber meshes. This device allows the production of continuous mesh samples with a width of 0.5 m. Fibers are drawn from a polymer solution that is spread on the wire electrospinning electrode in high voltage and collected on a carrier material placed below the wire collecting electrode. Siliconized paper was used as it is a well-known carrier material with low adhesion between the made fibers and the carrier material. The electrospinning process was controlled by adjusting the device (electrode distance, intensity of high voltage, production speed = speed of carrier material, speed of carriage spreading the polymer solution on wire, etc.) and environment of the process (temperature, relative humidity, airflow rate, etc.).

Polyamide 6 (PA6) and polyacrylonitrile (PAN) were chosen as materials for the initial lab-scale tests. PA6 was dissolved in a mixture of acetic acid and formic acid with a concentration of 12 wt%. PAN was dissolved in DMF with a solution of 10 wt%.

Before sample preparation, process parameters were established on laboratory scale equipment. The electrospinning process was adjusted to 100 kV in spinning chamber with an air temperature of 22 °C.

Fiber meshes were prepared with a basis weight of 1, 2 and 4 g/m², and two different fiber diameters 85 and 120 nm of PA6; 95 and 110 nm of PAN. The basis weight of the mesh is ruled by the speed of the carrier material. Samples with a length of 1.3-3m were produced. All samples were thick enough to be easy to handle. Samples were cut for the evaluation of their basis weight and taking SEM images. The rest of the samples was cut to A4 sheets and sent to **JKU** and **RWTH** for adhesion measurements.

Next to the production of fiber meshes, we started developing a method to obtain individual fibers and oriented meshes. Samples with very low thickness of the fiber layer were prepared by increasing the speed of the carrier material. Samples with a length of 1.3-3 m were prepared and consequently cut for the evaluation of their basis weight and taking SEM images. Samples produced at a higher speed could not be evaluated because the layer was so thin that it could not be peeled off the carrier material.

New approach was tested for the generation of oriented fibers; spinning fibers on a small aluminum tip. The resulting meshes show only partial alignment and defects. Further optimization of operating parameters is necessary here. **Image 2** shows the aluminum tip with fibers and a partially aligned fiber mesh with defects, obtained from the gap.

Image 2: A) Photograph of PAN fibers spun to an aluminum tip. B) Partially aligned PAN fibers with defects obtained from the air gap between collecting electrodes.

At **RWTH**, a method for microfluidic spinning of nano- and microfibers was developed. In microfluidic spinning, a concentric co-flow of two fluids is created with the polymer-bearing phase (spinning dope) in the center. Due to the laminar flow conditions in microfluidic channels, this co-flow is stable and allows the targeted solidification of the polymer; through photopolymerization, chemical crosslinking or solvent-nonsolvent exchange.

A method for the production of microfluidic chips for microfluidic spinning has been developed (see Lösberg *et al.* (2018)) that allows the inclusion of functional, 3D-spinnerets into conventional microfluidic channels. An overview over the method is shown in **Image 3**.

Image 3: Schematic overview over the process for printing spinnerets into microfluidic chips (see Lölsberg *et al.* (2018)).

The microfluidic chips used for the procedure are produced by replicating a master with polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS). The liquid elastomer is poured onto the master that carries the negative of the desired channel layout. After curing, the solidified elastomer is peeled off the master yielding a PDMS-slab that carries the desired channel layout on its bottom side. The channels are closed off with a microscopy cover glass that is plasma-bonded to the PDMS. Masters are printed with a two-photon lithography printer (Photonic GT, Nanoscribe GmbH, Germany).

A negative-tone liquid photoresist (IP-L 780, Nanoscribe GmbH, Germany) is loaded into the microfluidic channel using a syringe. The spinneret is printed through the glass slide directly into the channel with the two-photon lithography printer. The uncured photoresist, which surrounds the spinneret, is removed by flushing the channel with acetonitrile, leaving only the spinneret inside the microfluidic chip.

This method allows the rapid inclusion of CAD-designed spinnerets into microfluidic chips, leveraging the design freedom of rapid prototyping technologies. Until now, three types of spinnerets were produced; a simple spinneret, a dual-material spinneret and a spinneret for core-shell structured fibers. **Image 4** shows a SEM micrograph of a spinneret and a micrograph of the spinning process.

Image 4: A) SEM micrograph of a spinneret printed into a microfluidic channel. B) Micrograph of the spinning process, visualized with food coloring. (see Lölsberg *et al.* (2018))

For microfluidic spinning, the chip is connected to pressurized microfluidic reservoirs containing the spinning dope and shear fluid. The flow inside the chip is observed in an inverse microscope and controlled with a digital constant pressure system. The inlet pressures are

adjusted to achieve a stable co-flow of the fluids. The solidified fiber is collected from the opening of the outlet channel onto a rotating spindle.

Fibers were produced via non-solvent induced phase separation (NIPS) from polyacrylonitrile (PAN) and regenerated Bombyx mori silk. Alginate fibers were produced via ionic crosslinking. The material systems are summarized in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Material systems for lab scale microfluidic fiber spinning

Polymer type	Solvent	Polymer concentration [wt%]	Shear fluid	Mechanism
<i>B.mori</i> silk	HFIP	2	Ethanol / HFIP (2:1)	NIPS
Alginate	Water	1	CaCl ₂ / Water (748mM)	Ionic crosslinking
PAN	DMSO	2	Water / DMSO (2:1)	PIPS

With the established methods for electrospinning and microfluidic spinning, we have a versatile toolkit for the lab-scale production of fibers from various materials with various mechanisms. These fibers will allow us to further investigate the antiadhesive properties of structured substrate, to understand the mechanisms of adhesion, and to apply this knowledge to facilitate the production and handling of nanofibers from lab- to industrial scale.

Literature hints:

- Lölsberg, J., Linkhorst, J., Cinar, A., Jans, A., Kuehne, A.J.C. & Wessling, M. (2018) 3D Nanofabrication inside rapid prototyped microfluidic channels showcased by wet-spinning of single micrometre fibres. *Lab Chip*, 1341-1348.

2. Evaluation of Goals and Resulting Actions

This report has been published as a public report (PDF) in the dissemination section of the website of the **BioCombs4Nanofibers** project (<http://biocombs4nanofibers.eu>). Additionally, a reference to this report will be published on twitter and researchgate as project update for our followers.

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